

ISic1176

A koinon of priests honours [-?-] Lapiron, son of Diogenes

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object

block

Editor

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Autopsy

2011-06-15

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Halaesa. The stone was seen by Gualtherus (1624) in a building adjacent to the church of S. Maria dei Palazzi, but was already lost by the time of Castelli (1753). It was rediscovered c.1970 by Giacomo Scibona in the building adjacent to the church of S. Maria , where it formed part of the pavement of a 'stalla' (Scibona

2008b: 20).

Coordinates

37.996548, 14.261780

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa, inventory ME 20221

Physical Description

An incomplete block of limestone, damaged on the left, right, below and at the rear; only the front face and upper surface are preserved. The nature of the upper surface suggests that at least one more block originally stood on top of this one; at least one deliberately cut indentation is visible on the upper surface, presumably for the joining of blocks.

Dimensions

Height 19 cm

Width 30 cm

Depth 33 cm

Layout

Three lines of Greek text are preserved: the state of the stone means that the beginning and end of all three lines is lost, and at least one further line could have been lost below. If there were any lines above these, they would have been on a separate block of stone.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are regularly cut, with deep terminations to the strokes rather than extended serifs. Epsilon has a shorter middle bar, detached from the main vertical; omicron is very slightly smaller than the other letters; omega is almost, or completely closed, with a slightly elliptical rather than purely circular form.

Letter heights:

Lines 1-3: 25-30 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. [---][τὸ κοινὸν τῶν ἱερέων[ν][---]
2. [---][Διογ]ένεος Λαπίρων[α][---]
3. [---][εὐνοίας ἔνεκ]εν καὶ εὐεργεσί[α][---]

Apparatus

Text based on autopsy

Translation (en)

The koinon of the priests (honours) [-?-] Lapiron, son of Diogenes, on account of his good works and good will.

Translation (it)

Il koinon dei sacerdoti (onora) [-?-] Lapiron, figlio di Diogenes, per la sua benevolenza e munificenza.

Commentary

The restoration of τὸ κοινὸν in line 1 is virtually certain, on the basis of the bronze inscription in honour of Nemenios (SEG 59.1100 [http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/1874-6772_seg_a59_1100]), as Scibona recognised (2009a: 108). That text however refers to τὸ κοινὸν τῶν ἱερέων τοῦ Ἀπολλωνος, and although it is possible that this text continued in that way, it is notable that lines 2 and 3 only require a single additional letter, and the addition of τοῦ Ἀπολλωνος would unbalance the layout of the text. At the same time, most of the other honorific texts of the Hellenistic period from Halaesa are dedications 'to all the gods' (Θεοῖς πᾶσι) and if that phrase stood at the start of line 1, then the text would be lengthy, but symmetrical (especially as a longer amount of text is lost from the beginning of line 2, and at least 10 letters are lost from the first part of line 3); alternatively the phrase may have appeared on a second block above. It is also possible that a further line followed below the surviving text, with the phrase, as found in the Nemenios bronze, τᾶς εἰς αὐτον.

ISic1175 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1175>] records a Diogenes Lapiron, son of Diogenes. It is very likely that one should restore the patronymic here as Diogenes, but we cannot assume that this is the same individual, even though editors since Franz (CIG no.5596) have simply restored the name in full (Prestianni Giallombardo 2012: 179 is more cautious). The family is attested in several other inscriptions (ISic1175 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1175>] , ISic0800 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0800>] , ISic3571 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3571>]) and in Cicero (Verr. 2.2.19 [<http://data.perseus.org/citations/urn:cts:latinLit:phi0474.phi005.perseus-lat1:2.2.19-28>], for which see Facella 2006: 229-241.

The koinon of priests is presumably the same one as that responsible for the bronze in honour of Nemenios (SEG 59.1100 [http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/1874-6772_seg_a59_1100]) – an otherwise unattested but very large (825+ members) association of priests of Apollo, apparently centred upon Halaesa (for the sanctuary of Apollo at Halaesa, see Facella 2006: 318-22 and A.M. Prestianni Giallombardo, *Divinita e culti in Halaesa Archonidea*, in *Quarte Giornate Internazionali di studi sull'area elima* (Pisa 2003), vol. 3, pp. 1075-81). We do not know if the association was based only in Halaesa, or extended across other communities in the area or even across Sicily. If the former, then, it must have been more or less equivalent to the entire citizen body of Halaesa, and both this text and the Nemenios bronze show that it was able to erect honours in the principal public spaces of the city (for the koinon, see Scibona 2009 and G. Manganaro in *Da Halaesa ad Agathyrnum* (Santa'Agata di Militello 2011), 33-68).

The text cannot be dated precisely, but belongs to the second or first century BC on the basis of the form of the inscription and the style of the letters (the Nemenios bronze belongs to the first century BC).

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